

Teaching and Learning Focused Faculty Promotion in Philippine State Universities using the Teaching Excellence Framework

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Abstract. This article discusses the idea of integrating the Teaching Excellence Framework as a tool to solve the problem of salary stagnation of faculty members whose focus is on teaching and learning. Currently state universities use a metric-based system in faculty promotion which weighs research more than instruction causing faculty members to experience salary stagnation and slow movement in their promotion. The author discussed the four levels of the framework and highlighted practices from different literature in the country in accordance with these levels. The study used review of related literature and meta-analysis as the primary method in gathering the information needed. The RRL came from published local and international studies, news and report articles posted in websites, and from government documents. The outcomes and discussion followed a format of discussing the level based on the Royal Academy of Engineering who created the framework, followed by practices in the Philippines, the sphere of impact, promotion criteria and the evidence, and a concluding paragraph. An important finding of this study is the adoption of this framework with other universities in the ASEAN region and other international universities. According to these universities they have bridged the gap between research and instruction and leverage the pedagogical strategies of their faculty members. The framework also promoted diversification among faculty members, and a socially justified metric of salary increase and promotion.

Introduction

Producing more value per hour of work is rewarded by stagnant or worse, declining salary wages for the working class. This is the condition of our working class in the Philippines as explained in research facilitated by the IBON Foundation (2023) titled, “Filipino workers productivity increasing but real wages falling.” The research provides data on work productivity that shows Filipinos have increased their working value which are real gains for the company they are working for. Despite this increase, workers are not compensated for their work value. This creates an unequal economy as these increased work values contribute to the macroeconomy of the country while they [the working class] only see minimal or no improvements to their real salaries. This is a gap that must be addressed through legislation to promote social justice and inclusivity between workers, owners, investors, and the government.

With the increase of salary through legislation can be passed, it is the challenge for private and government owned industries to implement their own merits in the promotion process. The philosophy of promotion must be based on performance which is the generally accepted principle. But the question of performance-based promotion or pay, does it really increase the productivity of the workers? This is the inquiry that was answered in a column published in Business News Daily in 2023. It reviews articles if performance-based salary or promotion is really a factor in increasing a worker’s

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productivity. According to the literature a performance-based pay increases work motivation and their productivity level. The section also highlights that increased productivity is linked when employees are well informed of the merits of this pay or promotion or simply called, transparent communication. These merits must be aligned with the organization's goal and vision.

The teaching industry has been growing throughout the years, from basic education, technical vocational, undergraduate and even graduate studies. The free and accessibility of higher education increased the number of students all throughout various disciplines and programs, thus the need for higher education instructors, lecturers, and professors has been so demanding that the issue of salary increase is being put on the table. Salary increases in state universities have been an issue a long time ago, now we are faced with another issue - the merit system. Like other industries the academe, especially in government funded colleges and universities is no exception in the issue of delayed salaries, politics in promotion, and the point of this study - the merit system, which focuses more on research rather than teaching.

This issue is highlighted in the study of Bentley, P., & Ashwin, P. (2025), looking only at the title of their work we can attest to the findings of their study that teachers in higher education are not being promoted just by teaching alone. Their paper discusses how teachers in higher education are being promoted only focusing on their research outputs. Also it is proposed to prioritize education-focused promotion. Education of teaching focused lecturers have felt isolated and also struggle with recognition and promotion while education institutions hail educators that are more focused on research. The researchers noted that teaching is being neglected in the promotional process and offers a solution by separating the merits for promotion in education and research focused areas.

This problem was also stated by Chen C.Y. (2015), where education institutions have prioritized research outputs over teaching abilities especially lecturers who had publications in world leading index citations such as Scopes and Web of Sciences. It also revealed that research is an easy ticket for lecturers who are not that good in teaching, teaching and service only became a prerequisite for these lecturers. According to the study, faculty members view research not as contributing to the body of knowledge, but as an opportunity for them to advance their career. This has been the trend not only for some countries, but for the majority of the countries, research is hailed as a process of career advancement because it became the reward system for government funding and the pressure for an institution to be able to enter the world ranking.

In the Philippines, this kind of "publish or perish" practice has become rampant in state colleges and universities even the locally funded government colleges has already adapted this practice, according to Villasor T.Q. (2013) 's opinion column published in *Inquirer*, he asks a question and is also the title of the column, "How metrics, research downgrade teaching?" This simple question highlights the metrics used in universities that emphasizes research over teaching ability of lecturers or instructors. According to him, some faculty members are reported to have increased stress level and job dissatisfaction when teaching excellence is undervalued compared to the importance given to research performance during promotions.

This paper would clarify that in any way will not debunk that research is not important or teaching is more important. The Philippine Higher Education system believes in the tripartite goal - instruction, research, and extension, and must be given separate importance. The problem stated in the earlier paragraphs is that education or instruction centered performance by faculty members is not given an opportunity to have a separate metric in performance-based pay and promotion. The goal of the paper is to use a framework that focuses on teaching and instruction to identify the current condition, challenges and issues of our promotion metrics, the basis for faculty promotion and what do other researchers and education scientists recommend to each phase or area of the framework.

With these justifications, the author lead to the development of the topic, Teaching and Learning Focused Faculty Promotion in Philippine State Universities using the Teaching Excellence Framework

Methodology

A conceptual framework provides a map for the researcher and readers of the study on how the study will play out and how the variables will be treated. For this study, the researcher used the Teaching Excellence Framework, a framework developed by Dr. Ruth Graham of the Royal Academy of Engineering in April 2018.

Teaching Excellence Framework

The framework (see figure no. 1) has 4 progressive levels that a university educator must progress that can be attained through evidence. According to Dr. Graham the framework can be used by universities as a basis for appraisal and promotion thus providing a guide for metric tool creation that can be used in faculty promotions. Each level is called “teaching achievement” and must address the three components; (1) impact of the teacher in teaching and learning, (2) promotion criteria, and (3) forms of evidence to demonstrate teaching and learning.

The sphere of impact is composed of four areas namely the students, academic colleagues, local or educational environment, and the national and local education community which corresponds to each level of the teaching excellence framework. The promotion criteria involves the attitudes and delivery for level 1, skills and collaboration level 2, leadership and knowledge for level 3, and influence for level 4. Lastly, the forms of evidence, there are different documents or reports that can be used per level to determine a lecturer’s teaching ability. It can be self assessment, measure of a student’s learning, professional activities, peer evaluation and recognition, etc.

This framework shall be used all throughout the study to identify if state universities have been doing these approaches and what other researchers can tell on how to improve or recommend ideas to implement these levels of promotion focusing on teaching and instruction.

Figure No. 1. Teaching Excellence Framework

Results and Discussion

Using the teaching excellence framework, the study investigated the current situation of the Philippine State Universities on how they integrate each level and also the sphere of impact they provide. The teaching excellence framework as the title suggests focuses on how educators in higher education can be more effective and become excellent in the practice of teaching.

Effective Teacher

The first level of teaching excellence is the effective teacher, it focuses on the ability of the educator to have impact on his/her students. This involves the teaching approach, effective delivery of materials, and creating a positive learning environment. According to the faculty manual of the University of the Philippines - Diliman (n.d.) as published on their official website, the first requirement for any faculty member to be considered in any promotion is a good performance or a very satisfactory remark in the teaching/ mentoring performance. Those faculty members with low results, unsatisfactory attendance record shall be given low priority in faculty promotion.

In the Philippines, effective teaching is less acknowledged and has a lighter weight in faculty promotion as found in the study of Bentor, M. (2016). According to Bentor, the promotion of teaching personnel is tightly bound to the research and extension services and has less importance on the teaching effectiveness of the faculty. Despite having lesser importance in

faculty promotion, teaching covers much of the time of the faculty members as mentioned by Medallon, M. (2005), faculty members are given too much work load on teaching that they do not have spare time to do research and service. This is the reason also why teachers in higher education request a lighter time in teaching to provide them an opportunity to do their research. These studies only underscore the need to evaluate faculty members against their ability to teach since it takes up their time so much and teaching is their first responsibility in any university.

To understand the possible criteria in this level and what forms of evidences can be used a study conducted by Patacsil, F, et al (2022), shows the result of a qualitative study for a state university in Northern Luzon showcasing an open ended questions for students to share their experiences and the teaching strategies of their teachers. With this study we could see that the primary impact is on the students. The results of the study show that effective teaching according to the students constitutes classroom delivery and comprehension, understanding the lessons as done by the faculty or mastery of the topic, the ability of the faculty to explain complicated ideas, good communication skills, and moderate interaction with the students.

With regards to evidence, a teaching framework was developed by Aquino and Chavez (2022) suggesting tools that administrations can use to measure the teaching effectiveness of the faculty in higher education. This involves classroom observation, the teaching pedagogy/ style, student's performance (grades, tests, performance tasks), and results of the outcomes-based education (OBE alignment, course outcomes, activities, and assessments).

Skilled and Collegial Teacher

The next level of teaching excellence is the skilled and collegial or collaborative teacher. According to the official document of the Royal Academy who published this framework, this level's sphere of impact is the teacher's academic colleagues, his/her co faculty and supervisors. This level involves the teacher honing their teaching skills and the ability to collaborate and mentor others promoting teaching and learning excellence across all disciplines.

This practice of being skillful in the teaching field and being collaborative is actually a practice in secondary education and in some higher education institutions. In a study of Gamboa, R. (2022), it revealed that in one particular state university using the collaborative approach resulted in a high teaching effectiveness factor. Faculty members shared their ideas, best practices, and they would have joint practice in teaching. Also the study provides insights that faculty members are not only skillful in teaching, but they are also collegially engaged. One of the highlights of the study is that skillful teaching in the classroom is not the only factor that contributes to high effective teaching, but also collegial work with faculty members (high correlational result).

With regards to mentoring, a positive outlook on teachers being mentors to junior faculty members was the result of a study conducted by Gutierrez, M. (2016). In her study it revealed that mentorship was part of a collegial program in a medicine school. Mentors were viewed as content experts and provided guidance in their field and academic work. One of the highlights of her study was junior faculty members without mentors had low rates of teaching and administrative effectiveness unlike those who have mentors. This only shows that mentorship is a part of a successful collegial step on becoming an effective teacher.

In order to be promoted to this level there are criteria that must be attained. In the study of Bogasan J. and Poja, D. (2025) they have stated that a skillful teacher can adapt to a changing environment, collaborator, life long learner, a role model to other faculty members, and average to advance knowledge of using technology in delivering learning. For a teacher to be considered as a collaborator which is highlighted in their study as the central quality of a teacher, one must have the ability to work well with other faculty members, sharing ideas and best practices, engaging oneself to the community and school to better serve the students and betterment of the learning process.

A faculty member can be promoted to this level if he/she can provide evidence that determines the practices indicated in the criteria. An article published in Taylor and Francis has provided an analysis of evidence that faculty members may present to prove that they are skillful and collegial. For skillful teachers, they may present observation tools, rating scales, portfolios, etc. This evidence will capture the faculty's skillful performance in teaching doing techniques or practices that are beyond the general practice. For collegial it may include feedback, reflection, and results of the collaborative discussion from peer groups. Despite this evidence, the author emphasizes that the tools must be reliable and validated. Also, highlighting the importance of being transparent in the evaluation process of these tools (van der Schaaf, M., et al, 2019).

Institutional Leader in Teaching and Learning

Third level is divided into two parts, the first one is the institutional leader in teaching and learning and the other is the scholarly teacher. Both are in the same level due to the purpose of becoming a scholar and a leader. For the first part, this means that an academic teacher is not now bound in the classroom, but the teacher makes an effort to lead his co faculty members in teaching and learning within and beyond the classroom and institution.

This practice is not new in the context of the Philippines. Higher education institutions have a strong organizational structure of teachers in administrative and leadership positions especially in academics. In a study conducted by Sumena A., et al (2025) they have analyzed the responses of academic leaders on how they see themselves besides their administrative duties. The respondents's theme was that leadership position in the higher education is a huge responsibility to promote quality education, responsible for assuring the alignment of the program outcomes in the curriculum, design and support strategies for teaching and learning within their respective institutions, and to lead their faculty members in engaging with trainings, seminars, and workshops that will enhance their teaching capabilities. It was also revealed that academic leaders use tools in assessing their faculty by using classroom observations and providing feedback. This only shows that a teacher in this level to be promoted has the ability to lead his/her faculty members by using leadership values that aim to promote teaching and learning excellence.

An educator of this level must perform best practices to improve the teaching and learning environment of his/ her colleagues. These practices have been exercised by school administrators and academic leaders in the Philippines as provided in the research of Aquino, J.M. (2024). A framework was proposed by Aquino to assure quality in instructional leadership. Creating this framework involved gathering qualitative data from different top performing institutions. In the result it shows that academic leaders show a core responsibility on teaching and learning and aligning curriculum with standards and licensure examinations. It is important to note that academic leaders are data driven meaning they base their decisions on results of exams, internal evaluations, accreditation feedback, and licensure results. Also, the research shows that institutional leaders provide an environment where faculty members are engaged in their development having regular training, seminars, and workshops. Lastly, institutional leaders build an atmosphere of collaboration and teamwork.

Promoting faculty members on this level must possess the criteria needed. Andaya, J., and Quinito, D. (2025) highlighted the features that a faculty member is ready to be considered as an institutional leader in teaching and learning. A faculty member must be ready to assist or help new and existing faculty members and are willing to provide their own experiences, skills, time, and expertise on a subject matter. The second skill is that the faculty must have a strong communication skill, the faculty must be able to transcend ideas, willingness to listen, accepting opinions, and providing constructive feedback. Third criteria that is often overlooked is the expertise and having a deep knowledge of the discipline and program and the ability to have continuous professional and educational development. Lastly, the faculty must be able to adapt to the changing environment of the institution and the external factors.

Evidence in this level must provide data that focuses on leadership and management capabilities of a faculty member. According to the studies mentioned earlier they have provided evidence that can be used. In Aquino, J.M. (2024)., documents indicating a teacher's involvement in accreditation, quality assurance activities, and assuming leadership roles, such as program chair and head of activity of the school. For Sumena A., et al (2025) it could be records of classroom observations, mentoring instructions, and development feedback. Sumena also included records of participation and contribution in curriculum development, syllabus creation, and other instructional contributions. Lastly, Andaya, J., and Quinito, D. (2025) suggest that institutions may create their own set or list of requirements that best measures a faculty's capability in promoting them to a level where they can be considered as institutional leaders.

Scholarly Teacher

The second part of level three is the scholarly teacher. A scholarly teacher impacts the academic community by contributing to the body of knowledge in education and to be specific in pedagogy. An important distinction between institutional leadership and scholarly teacher is that the latter focuses its impact on his/her educational environment while the other focuses its impact on educational knowledge, but they both share the same goal and that is to advance teaching and learning using their leadership and research skills. A scholarly teacher conducts studies on how to improve pedagogy and has a firm understanding of conducting research and also has an in-depth knowledge of the pedagogical theories, knowledge, and

application. This educator influences the content of the pedagogical approach by well informed data and evidence gathered in research.

In the Philippine context this is coined as SoTL or Scholarship of Teaching and Learning as provided in the study of Sison, R. (2014) published and presented at De La Salle University, that SoTL is only a new concept being practiced in the country and it is a research and evidence led action that promotes effective pedagogical approach. The research highlights that findings of a scholarly teacher must be made public, peer reviewed, and utilized by others especially the academe. The author argues that having the right SoTL framework will provide a guide in creating institutional policy such as changes in workload, mentoring programs, funding allocation, and faculty promotion. The point of a scholarly teacher is to promote teaching and learning excellence using research and evidence based practices that will lead to institutional policy and outcome utilization.

Other researchers provide some techniques on how to enhance the scholarly experience. Yong, P. and Peng, Y. (2025) have identified that teachers lack time to do scholarly teaching or do research due to the teaching workload, that is the reason why they have conducted the study and have revealed some ways how to practice this level. The first to have peer support, teachers can help one another in gathering data from the students, having peer evaluation, and mentoring. Another is the teaching reflection, this is the process of the teacher analyzing the lessons being taught and the student's responses, third is integrating research and teaching in the classroom practice. Making classroom issues and challenges to research problems and having them as the subject of the research. Next is the participation in training and seminars and having instructions aligned with the program and institutional objectives.

The criteria for a scholarly teacher may differ from authors and other researchers, but the study of Potter, M., and Kustra, E., (2015) provides a simple four point criteria for a faculty to be promoted to this position. According to them, a faculty is considered to be a scholar if he/she has the expertise in pedagogical approach of a particular field or discipline. Second, a scholarly teacher is a systematic thinker and gathers evidence as part of his/her basis in making informed decisions before applying. Next is that all instructional decisions that affect the teaching of the faculty and learning of the students are well established on research and validated criteria of knowledge inquiry. Lastly, a scholarly teacher is engaged in long term discussions on improvement and feedback.

The University of Colorado, Boulder in the United States suggests standards, evidence or processes that a faculty must dispense in order to assess a faculty before promoting to this level. According to the study, there are six scholarly standards. First is the ability to determine clear goals. As a scholarly teacher the faculty must be able to identify the goals of the inquiry or its objectives. Other standards are having adequate preparation, appropriate methods, having significant results of the research, providing an effective presentation that will properly communicate to the faculty, and having a reflective critique. Mostly these standards can be presented in a portfolio (Finkelstein, N., 2017)

National/ Global Leader in Teaching and Learning

The last level in the teaching excellence framework is the national/ global leader in teaching and learning. According to the official article of the Royal Academy it was described as the ability of the faculty member to do all other three levels and have an impact in a national level and become a figure of excellence in teaching and learning in the international community. This faculty has influence in international platforms and is known for advancing ideas and practices that leverage the pedagogy of classes in higher education.

To understand this level, it is necessary to study the characteristics of some acclaimed international figures in teaching and learning that came from the Philippines, one of which is the Bernido Couple, Dr. Christopher C. Bernido and Dr. Ma. Victoria Carpio-Bernido. They both received the prestigious Ramon Magsaysay Award for their incredible work titled, CVIF Dynamic Learning Program (DLP). According to the official website of the Ramon Magsaysay Award Foundation (2010), The couple developed a new way of teaching science to poor and remote young Filipino students in the province of Bohol. The program is simple, 70 percent of the class time is devoted to student driven activities anchored in the target learning programs guided by learning plans and performance tasks. Also the program used a "parallel classes scheme" where there are 3 simultaneous classes handled by one expert instructor and assisted by facilitators. This was the start of their journey in building quality education and solving the problem of insufficient number of physics teachers in the country. It impacted societies and influenced the national community of educators to reinvent the wheel of teaching and learning.

The criteria for this promotion in universities doesn't need to be a recipient of a high governing body. In the official article of the teaching excellence framework, it was stated that the general criteria for this level is that a faculty must have a high impact contribution in the advancement of teaching and learning through research and knowledge contribution, informing the academic community from the institution, national, and international about the strategies in effective teaching and learning, also is a recognized authority in his/her field and in teaching and lastly is known for having a leadership role in collaborating with other institutions locally and abroad that advances strategies in the academe. These criterions were seen during the Metrobank's Search for Outstanding Teacher Award.

As presented in the official website of the Department of Education (2019), it can be said that the recipients share common practices that led them to be awarded as one of the Outstanding Teachers of the country. The recipients have a common goal in designing the teaching and learning experiences of the students, being well versed and gaining deep knowledge of their subject, discovering things in the field of science that lead to the contribution to the body of knowledge, and bringing impact to the national and international community of educators. These traits constitute a national and global leader in teaching and learning.

Conclusion and Implications

The Framework as used by International Universities

Notable universities in the ASEAN region and in other international countries have already used the teaching excellence framework as their basis for promotion. Different universities have their own techniques and ways on how they implement the framework. One example is the University of Twente in the Netherlands. In a published article by van der Veen (2018) the university used the framework for those faculty members who are focused on teaching and learning and also on education - research mixed faculty members. The university made a 4 level approach from basic teaching, senior teaching, and higher levels that focuses on leadership in education and scholarly teaching and learning which is the highest.

At the National University of Singapore (NUS), they have redesigned their metrics in promoting their faculty using the teaching excellence framework to address the gap of teachers that are more focused on teaching and learning. The promotion revolved in the concept of "sphere of influence" and used evidence that can be used to provide justification for the promotion. Evidence includes self assessment, student evaluation, peer assessment and the actual achievements of the students. The university hired external peer reviewers to monitor the effectiveness of this process (NUS, n.d.).

Another ASEAN region university that had a great impact in using this framework is the Universiti Teknologi Malaysia (UTM). According to Graham (2025) the author of the article, UTM addressed the issue of its faculty in revising its system to promote diversity in academic careers. This move signifies an importance in the field of teaching and learning from the research dominant approach. One of the outcomes of this change is that the university has produced faculty profiles that contributed to the excellence of teaching, crafting of curriculum, and improvement in pedagogical strategies of the faculty. The teaching learning focused promotion also included the scholar teacher where faculty members do research to improve their teaching.

This change of structure in faculty promotion in the international community has proven to promote diversity among faculty, being more student-centered, honing the pedagogical approach of faculty, and becoming experts in their own disciplines.

The Possibility of Implementing the Framework in the Philippines

Currently the Philippines has no adopted framework such as the teaching excellence framework as their basis for faculty promotion. The faculty promotion in the country uses guidelines for the promotion process such as the National Budget Circular 461 (DBM, 1998) for State Universities where it focuses on instruction, research, and extension. On this guideline, research is given more emphasis over the two. For thUniversity of the Philippines, they have another guideline and a different system that focuses on teaching, scholarly work, service to the university, and professional development.

Based on the studies mentioned in the discussion it can be concluded that the teaching for excellence framework can bridge the gap between faculty members whose expertise are on teaching and learning with those faculty who are research focused. Since there are no existing universities or colleges that use this framework it can be considered as an input for faculty

promotion and can be utilized nationally or by private institutions. This can also contribute as a solution to the salary stagnation of faculty members who again are focused on delivering learning and who are not research focused.

The Framework as a Tool in Solving Salary Stagnation

Solving the economic problem in the academe such as salary decrease and stagnation is not a common issue in state colleges and universities. The adoption of this framework is not just to provide a solution to these problems, but it conveys two issues that need to be addressed. First is the issue of the current metric and qualification itself, where research is focused more on promotion while teaching and learning has a lesser focus. This builds a haven for faculty researchers and creates an elite circle of only faculty members who know how to write, present, and publish in international and prestigious publications without acknowledging the same importance of the instruction. Second is the salary stagnation, having said that faculty members who do not do research and only focus on their teaching career will have a hard time to build their profile for their promotion. The adoption of this framework can bridge the gap between promotion and stagnation, promoting an equal and diversified teaching environment and leveraging a worker or a faculty member's purchasing power in this economy.

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Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

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Appendices

Appendix A. Literature Mapping

A comprehensive mapping of the 25 studies reviewed in this paper is provided in Excel format as a supplementary file. The literature matrix organizes the reviewed studies by Teaching Excellence Framework level, research focus, key findings, methodology, and geographic context. Readers may download Appendix A - Literature Mapping Table from the supplementary materials associated with this article and from the project's GitHub repository by clicking on this [link](#).